

Combining Histology, Medical imaging and molecular data for medical prognosis and diagnosis

Agent(CHIMERA-agent): Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Combining Histology, Medical imaging and molecular data for medical prognosis and diagnosis
Agent(CHIMERA-agent)

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

CHIMERA-agent

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Prostate cancer is among the most common cancers worldwide. Each year, about 1.4 million men are diagnosed, and their care requires radiologists, pathologists, and oncologists to integrate information across multiple modalities, including multiparametric MRI, whole-slide images (WSI) and longitudinal clinical variables across the entire patient journey[1]. At every step, uncertainty is introduced: modalities arrive at different time points, are stored in other systems, may be missing, and can be contradictory. Yet most AI tools remain siloed, single-modality systems that rarely demonstrate how they combine evidence or reason in a clinically meaningful way.

Last year, CHIMERA (Combining Histology, Medical imaging and molecular data for medical prognosis and diagnosis) introduced multimodal cancer benchmarking at MICCAI 2025[2]. While it integrated MRI WSI in prostate cancer, it did not fully reflect real clinical practice, where data are rarely fully paired and complete, and where decisions must be made before downstream information (e.g., prostatectomy pathology, genomics, follow-up) is available. We therefore propose an updated benchmark, CHIMERA-agent, that bridges this gap by covering the full clinical continuum from early MRI-based decision-making to long-term biochemical recurrence prediction, explicitly emphasizing missingness, fragmentation, and cross-modality conflict.

CHIMERA-agent is structured as a staged clinical scenario for prostate cancer patients that mirrors real-world care. AI agents are sequentially exposed to incomplete and evolving patient information, starting with multiparametric MRI and basic clinical variables to support early diagnostic and biopsy decisions, followed by histopathology, treatment context, and longitudinal follow-up for biochemical recurrence risk estimation. At each stage, agents must operate under realistic constraints, including missing modalities, delayed availability of

downstream data, and potentially conflicting evidence across sources. The challenge is designed as an agentic multimodal challenge that benchmark the reasoning capabilities of AI models in clinical decision-making. Each question or clinical scenario requires participants to submit not only predictions but also structured reasoning traces explaining how available evidence is interpreted and integrated. These reasoning outputs are systematically evaluated alongside task performance, enabling direct assessment of large language model-based agents for clinical reasoning, transparency, and guideline alignment under realistic conditions of uncertainty and incomplete data.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Multimodal AI, Agent-based systems, Computational Pathology, MRI, Clinical Decision Support, Human-AI Interaction, Precision Oncology

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

CHIMERA-agent is the first multimodal benchmark to explicitly model the prostate cancer patient journey. It addresses two fundamental real-world challenges: incomplete pairing across modalities, where MRI, pathology, and clinical data are frequently missing or fragmented, and longitudinal decision-making, where evidence accrues over time and clinical decisions must be made before downstream information becomes available. Crucially, the benchmark also evaluates the reasoning underlying each decision step, moving beyond outcome prediction to transparent, clinically grounded decision-making.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

CHIMERA-agent targets real-world prostate cancer care, where clinical decisions are made sequentially under incomplete and evolving information. The challenge tasks span the full patient journey, from early MRI-based diagnosis and biopsy decision-making, through pre-treatment risk stratification and pathology prediction, to post-prostatectomy recurrence prognosis and longitudinal follow-up. Each task reflects a concrete clinical decision point faced by radiologists, pathologists, and oncologists, requiring integration of MRI, biopsy findings, whole-slide pathology, molecular data, and clinical variables when available. By explicitly modeling missing modalities, repeated measurements, and conflicting evidence, CHIMERA-agent evaluates AI agents in application scenarios that closely mirror routine multidisciplinary decision-making rather than idealized, fully paired datasets.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

The CHIMERA-agent challenge will be organized as part of a dedicated CHIMERA workshop at MICCAI 2026, focusing on multimodal, agent-based AI for clinically grounded decision-making in prostate cancer.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

A half- or full-day slot is required because CHIMERA-agent goes beyond a standard benchmarking challenge and includes multiple sequential tasks that reflect the full prostate cancer patient journey. The workshop program will combine an overview of the clinical scenarios, detailed explanation of the multimodal datasets and evaluation protocol, and presentations from top-performing teams highlighting different agent designs and reasoning strategies. In addition, dedicated time is needed for discussion with clinicians to assess the clinical plausibility of model reasoning and decision-making, which is a central objective of the challenge. The extended format enables meaningful interaction between AI researchers and clinical experts and supports in-depth discussion of multimodal integration, missing data handling, and transparent reasoning, which cannot be adequately covered in a short session.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Based on the previous CHIMERA challenge at MICCAI 2025, we expect a similar or slightly increased level of participation. Last year, the challenge received approximately 25 submissions, and the associated workshop attracted around 40 in-person attendees. Given the expanded scope of CHIMERA-agent, its agent-based focus, and the release of baseline tools to lower entry barriers, we anticipate 25–35 teams submitting results and 40–60 participants attending the workshop.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Similar to the original CHIMERA challenge, we plan to coordinate a joint overview paper summarizing the CHIMERA-agent benchmark and challenge results, including task design, datasets, evaluation metrics, and a comparative analysis of participating methods. The focus will be on multimodal integration, robustness to missing and longitudinal data, and agent-level clinical reasoning policies.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If

you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The CHIMERA-agent challenge will be hosted on the Grand Challenge platform, with computing infrastructure provided via AWS. Data access will be facilitated through AWS data storage.

For the on-site workshop at MICCAI, only standard conference equipment is required, including a projector and screen, microphones for speakers and audience interaction, and internet connectivity to support online participants.

TASK 1: MRI-Only Diagnostic Decision.

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Early prostate cancer diagnosis relies heavily on multiparametric MRI, together with basic clinical variables such as age and prostate-specific antigen (PSA), to decide whether a biopsy is warranted. From a biomedical perspective, this decision aims to detect clinically significant prostate cancer while avoiding unnecessary invasive procedures, and is typically made before histopathological confirmation is available.

From a technical perspective, this task focuses on MRI-based risk estimation and decision support under unimodal and limited information. In Task 1 of the CHIMERA-agent challenge, models must estimate the probability of clinically significant prostate cancer and recommend whether biopsy is indicated using only MRI-derived features (e.g., PI-RADS, lesion characteristics, capsular contact) and basic clinical measures. Ground truth labels are derived from histopathology, enabling objective evaluation against definitive pathological outcomes. To lower the entry barrier, a validated MRI prostate zone segmentation tool is provided as an optional resource; participants are free to use this tool or develop their own approaches.

The envisioned impact of this task is twofold. Biomedically, it supports more consistent, MRI-driven biopsy decision-making aligned with pathology ground truth. Technically, the challenge promotes the development of interpretable AI agents that combine imaging-based prediction with structured reasoning. Participants are expected to design a decision policy reflecting the clinical journey of a prostate cancer patient, orchestrating pretrained, modality-specific foundation models rather than training models from scratch. The required tools are provided by the organizers, allowing participants to focus on agent-level reasoning and decision support.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Multimodal AI, Agent-based AI, Prostate cancer, MRI-based diagnosis, Clinically significant prostate cancer, Biopsy decision support, Clinical reasoning

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Dr. Nadieh Khalili – Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

Prof. Geert Litjens – Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

PhD. Kimmo Kartasalo – Karolinska Institute, Sweden

Prof. Martin Eklund – Karolinska Institute, Sweden

Dr. MD. Max Ragusi (radiologist)– University Medical Center Utrecht, The Netherlands

Dr. Jolique van Ipenburg (pathologist) - Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Nadieh Khalili, Radboud University Medical Center (Radboudumc), The Netherlands
nadieh.khalili@radboudum.nl

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Clinicians are an integral part of the organizing team. For Task 1, expert radiologists are directly involved in defining the task, validating MRI-derived labels and features, and evaluating the reasoning provided by the top five performing teams.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

CHIMERA 2025: <https://chimera.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed during model development and training, including data curation (e.g., excluding training samples), preprocessing and pre-training or fine-tuning. No user interaction is allowed during inference on the hidden test set.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

External data and pre-trained models are permitted in this competition, provided they are freely and publicly accessible under a permissive open-source license. Examples of such licenses include the Creative Commons license (standard), GNU software or documentation license (standard), BSD license, MIT license, or Open Database license. If participants are uncertain whether a specific dataset's license qualifies as permissive, they should consult the challenge organizers for clarification.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 10 teams will be invited to be part of the challenge manuscript. In addition, we are actively seeking sponsorship for awards. We will provide prize incentives exclusively for open-source submissions. In addition, we will highlight and recognize teams that contribute reusable tools and methodologies to encourage knowledge sharing.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the submission. Only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed up to five co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when citing the overview paper after its publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Interested teams must register for the CHIMERA-agent challenge via chimera-agent.grand-challenge.org. After release of the training dataset, teams may develop their solutions using their own public or private computing resources. Submissions consist of a trained algorithm packaged as a Docker container, which is evaluated on a validation cohort. Teams may participate in one or multiple tasks.

During evaluation, algorithms are executed on the Grand Challenge platform, where performance is assessed on a hidden tuning cohort and rankings are updated on a live public leaderboard. All participating teams will be invited to submit their Docker containers for final evaluation on a held-out test set. Detailed instructions for container submission are provided by the platform. In addition, we will release baseline tools for prostate cancer zonal segmentation, and example inference Docker containers to facilitate participation.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to validate their results multiple times (up to 5) on a validation set before submitting the final results. This can also help participants ensure the submission is in the correct format. Only the best submission will be counted for the official validation ranking. Only a single test set submission will be allowed to avoid overfitting.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Announcement of challenge's opening: April 1th 2026

- Open for registration: April 1th, 2026
- Training data release: April 1th, 2026
- Validation phase start: May 15th, 2026
- Deadline for test set submission: September 1st, 2026
- Winner and invitation speakers: No later than September 7th, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Radboud University Medical Center approved this challenge protocol on 5/1/2016, with NO. 20162275. Contact person: Geert Litjens, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Science, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands; geert.litjens@radboudumc.nl

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation pipeline will be made public and open source after the launch of the challenge. We will provide a GitHub link for the code of evaluation metrics on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

:The participants are encouraged to upload their code to Github and share the Github link in the PDF submission file.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the prostate cancer prognosis challenge. Only organizing members of the challenge have access to the test case labels during and after the CHIMERA-agent challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final

biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of biological males aged 50 years and older who have undergone MRI scanning for prostate cancer.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The target cohort consists of biological males aged 50 years and older who have undergone MRI scanning for prostate cancer.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

multiparametric MRI

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

the MRIs (*****.mha where ***** stands for subject_id) and Psca

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

We will provide PSA, age for prostate patients

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

MRI of a prostate

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants must develop an algorithm that uses multiparametric prostate MRI together with basic clinical variables (e.g., age, PSA, PSA density, and prostate volume) to predict the probability of clinically significant prostate cancer (csPCa), with ground truth defined by histopathology. Based on this predicted risk, the algorithm should output a biopsy recommendation and provide structured reasoning that explains how MRI findings (such as PI-RADS scores, lesion characteristics, zonal anatomy, and capsular contact) and clinical information support the decision.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Reliability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

mpMRI Imaging: Acquired using a Siemens 3T scanner at both Radboudumc, Nijmegen, and CWZ, the Netherlands

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

mpMRI images were acquired in the axial plane using a Siemens 3T scanner with a standardized imaging protocol that included T1-weighted imaging for anatomical visualization, ADC maps derived from diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) to assess tissue diffusion characteristics, and DWI sequences with multiple b-values for detecting clinically significant prostate cancer.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training set originates from Radboud University Medical Center. The test set was obtained from Radboudumc, CWZ, Karolinska Institute, and several additional contributing institutes. The names of the latter will remain anonymous until final confirmation is obtained.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Prostate MRI examinations were acquired as part of routine clinical care and interpreted by board-certified radiologists with expertise in prostate MRI, following standard clinical guidelines (e.g. PI-RADS). No experimental acquisition procedures were involved.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Cases are weakly annotated, with positive cases defined by histopathology-confirmed clinically significant prostate cancer (csPCa), and negative cases defined negative PSA follow-up.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Participants are welcome to use publicly available datasets, including the PI-CAI benchmark (which provides over 1,000 training cases), to train and test their own models if desired. As the challenge is organized by Radboudumc, access to relevant tools and resources can be facilitated. However, the task does not require training models from scratch, as pretrained tools are provided. The primary focus of the evaluation is on agent-level reasoning and clinical decision-making rather than representation learning.

For this task, 400 cases with radiologist-annotated reasoning will be provided, comprising 75 training cases, 75 validation cases, and 250 test cases. Of the test cases, 100 originate from Karolinska Institute and serve as an external test set to assess generalizability across institutions.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

The radiology reports for all 400 cases are already available, and histopathology-derived ground truth for clinically significant prostate cancer is present. Reasoning annotations will be extracted from the reports and double-checked by radiologists.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The chosen data proportions reflect the agent-centric design of the task. As pretrained foundation models are provided, the training set is intended for calibration and policy design rather than model training from scratch, and therefore requires a limited number of cases. The validation set supports tuning and public feedback, while the majority of cases are reserved for the test set to enable robust and unbiased evaluation of agent-level reasoning and clinical decision-making. This allocation balances expert annotation effort with statistically meaningful assessment of reasoning performance on unseen data.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training data has real-world distribution. Participants should expect data with domain shift/from other institutions in validation and testing. We encourage participants to develop models that generalize well across centers despite domain shifts caused by differences in MRI parameters, staining. At the same time, we will try to match important characteristics of the development and testing cohorts as much as possible, such as age, Gleason grades, etc.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will publish 100 cases, multiparametric MRI specifically curated for this challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For all training, validation, and test cases, the reference annotation for clinically significant prostate cancer (csPCa) is derived from histopathology, using ISUP Grade Group ≥ 2 as the definition of csPCa. Negative cases are confirmed through longitudinal PSA follow-up.

Reasoning annotations describe the clinical decision logic underlying the reference outcome label. These reasoning statements are automatically extracted from structured radiology reports using large language models and subsequently validated by expert radiologists based on the available radiology reports and current clinical guidelines. The reasoning explicitly states the key evidence supporting the decision (e.g. MRI findings, lesion characteristics, biopsy grade when available). The same annotation procedure is applied consistently across training, validation, and test cases.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Prior to annotation, annotators were provided with a written annotation protocol describing the clinical objective of the task, the required outputs, and the definition of clinically significant prostate cancer (csPCa) according to established guidelines, aligned with PI-RADS v2.1.

Annotators were instructed to:

- Review the associated radiology reports for each case.
- Verify extracted structured MRI-derived variables (e.g. PI-RADS score, lesion presence and number, lesion location, zonal anatomy, capsular contact) and basic clinical variables when available.
- Review and validate reasoning statements automatically extracted using large language models.
- Write or refine one or two concise, clinically grounded reasoning sentences explaining the likelihood of csPCa and the biopsy recommendation, explicitly referencing key MRI findings and clinical context.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The ground truth of task 1 is from biopsy WSI and the uncertainty in Gleason Grade Group assignment may arise from sampling limitations in biopsy cores and inter-pathologist variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

NA

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The evaluation metric consists of two folds, reflecting (i) tool selection and prediction performance and (ii) quality of generated reasoning.

Fold 1: Predictive performance (tool selection and outcome prediction)

The first fold evaluates whether the agent selects the appropriate tool and produces accurate predictions. In this task, prostate cancer (PCa) performance is assessed using the standard AUROC metric, which serves as the primary metric for leaderboard ranking.

Fold 2: Reasoning similarity (non-ranking)

To assess similarity between generated reasoning and reference texts, we employ a composite similarity metric that captures semantic, conceptual, and lexical alignment. Semantic similarity is computed using cosine similarity between sentence embeddings extracted with PubMedBERT (NeuML/pubmedbert-base-embeddings). Biomedical concept overlap is quantified using Jaccard similarity over entities extracted with SciSpacy (en_core_sci_lg). Lexical overlap is assessed using simplified BLEU-4 (4-gram precision) and ROUGE-L (longest common subsequence F1).

The final similarity score is defined as:

$$S = \frac{1}{\sum} (\text{EmbeddingCosine} + 2 \cdot \text{EntityJaccard} + 3 \cdot (\text{BLEU-4} + \text{ROUGE-L}))$$

This metric is used for relative comparison of explanation text and does not measure factual correctness, causal reasoning, or clinical validity.

Expert review of reasoning (top-performing submissions)

For the top five submissions on the leaderboard, domain experts (radiologists) will conduct a qualitative review of the generated explanations. Reasoning will be scored based on predefined criteria, including clinical plausibility,

coherence, appropriate use of evidence, and absence of spurious or unsupported claims. Expert scores will be reported separately and will not affect leaderboard ranking.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The evaluation metrics were selected to reflect the dual objectives of the challenge: accurate agentic decision-making and clinically grounded reasoning.

Predictive performance is assessed using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC), which provides a threshold-independent measure of discrimination and is well suited for evaluating prostate cancer risk prediction and clinical decision support tasks under class imbalance. AUROC is widely used in clinical AI studies and aligns with the biomedical objective of correctly ranking patients by disease likelihood or risk.

Reasoning quality is evaluated using a composite similarity metric that captures semantic, conceptual, and lexical alignment between model-generated explanations and expert reference reasoning. This design reflects the clinical requirement that AI systems not only produce accurate predictions but also articulate reasoning that aligns with established medical knowledge and reporting conventions.

Expert qualitative review of reasoning for top-performing submissions complements the automated metrics by assessing clinical plausibility, coherence, and appropriate use of evidence, thereby contextualizing quantitative results and ensuring clinical relevance without influencing the leaderboard ranking.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The final score for each algorithm is computed as a weighted combination of predictive performance and reasoning metrics. For the top five submissions, clinician-evaluated reasoning scores are combined with the two automated reasoning metrics and averaged to obtain the final reasoning score.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The challenge explicitly targets agent-level reasoning and decision transparency, which are essential for clinical trust, interpretability, and safe deployment alongside strong diagnostic performance. Incorporating reasoning quality into the ranking encourages participants to develop agents that not only achieve high predictive accuracy but also generate explanations that are aligned with expert clinical reasoning.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The statistical analysis is designed to provide robust evaluation of patient-level risk prediction, biopsy decision-making, and agent-level reasoning. Performance is assessed on a held-out test set using threshold-independent and clinically meaningful metrics. Uncertainty and variability are quantified using non-parametric, resampling-based methods, which do not rely on distributional assumptions and are appropriate given the moderate sample size and heterogeneous clinical data. Reasoning performance is evaluated on a curated subset with expert annotations.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms is assessed using non-parametric percentile bootstrap resampling on the private test set. For each metric (e.g. ROC–AUC for risk prediction and Clinical Reasoning Agreement Score (CRAS) for reasoning evaluation), bootstrap samples are generated at the case level.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Ranking variability is evaluated using bootstrap-based ranking stability analysis. For each bootstrap resample of the test set, algorithms are re-ranked based on the primary metric

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability is evaluated using bootstrap-based ranking stability analysis. For each bootstrap resample of the test set, algorithms are re-ranked based on the primary metric

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using paired, non-parametric tests on the test set.

Differences in ROC–AUC are evaluated using bootstrap-based paired comparisons.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Cases with missing ground truth labels are excluded from evaluation.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All statistical analyses are performed using Python, primarily leveraging NumPy, SciPy, scikit-learn

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

These further analyses will be discussed in a publication after the challenge.

TASK 2: MRI + Biopsy Risk Stratification.

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In the subsequent step of the prostate cancer care pathway, following MRI and biopsy, clinicians assess whether definitive treatment is required or whether active surveillance is appropriate. Participants must develop an AI agent that integrates post-biopsy information—including MRI findings, biopsy pathology whole-slide images, and PSA-related clinical variables—to determine eligibility for active surveillance versus radical prostatectomy.

To lower the entry barrier, the organizers will provide an automated Gleason grading tool for biopsy whole-slide images, as well as an MRI-based prostate cancer detection tool, which participants may use or replace with their own approaches. The agent must output a binary recommendation (eligible / not eligible for active surveillance), accompanied by structured clinical reasoning that identifies key supporting evidence and explicitly highlights factors that contradict active surveillance, in accordance with established clinical guidelines (e.g. EAU/NCCN).

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Prostate cancer, Active surveillance, Clinical decision support, Multimodal AI, Explainable AI, Prostate MRI, Digital pathology, Gleason grading, Biopsy analysis, Guideline-based reasoning

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Nadieh Khalili – Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

Geert Litjens – Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

Kimmo Kartasalo – Karolinska Institute, Sweden

Martin Eklund – Karolinska Institute, Sweden

Jolique van Ipenburg, , pathologist– Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

Max Ragusi, radiologist – University Medical Center Utrecht, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Nadieh Khalili, Radboud University Medical Center (Radboudumc), The Netherlands

nadieh.khalili@radboudumc.nl

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Clinicians are an integral part of the organizing team. For Task 2, expert radiologists and pathologists are directly involved in defining the task, validating MRI-derived and pathology annotations, and evaluating the reasoning provided by the top five performing teams.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

CHIMERA 2025: <https://chimera.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed during model development and training, including data curation (e.g., excluding training samples), preprocessing, and pre-training or fine-tuning. No user interaction is allowed during inference on the hidden test set.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

External data and pre-trained models are permitted in this competition, provided they are freely and publicly accessible under a permissive open-source license. Examples of such licenses include the Creative Commons license (standard), GNU software or documentation license (standard), BSD license, MIT license, or Open Database license. If participants are uncertain whether a specific dataset's license qualifies as permissive, they should consult the challenge organizers for clarification.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 10 teams will be invited to be part of the challenge manuscript. In addition, we are actively seeking sponsorship for awards. We will provide prize incentives exclusively for open-source submissions. In addition, we will highlight and recognize teams that contribute reusable tools and methodologies to encourage knowledge sharing.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the submission. Only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed up to five co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when citing the overview paper after its publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Interested teams must register for the CHIMERA-agent challenge via chimera-agent.grand-challenge.org. After release of the training dataset, teams may develop their solutions using their own public or private computing resources. Submissions consist of a trained algorithm packaged as a Docker container, which is evaluated on a

validation cohort. Teams may participate in one or multiple tasks.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to validate their results multiple times (up to 5) on a validation set before submitting the final results. This can also help participants ensure the submission is in the correct format. Only the best submission will be counted for the official validation ranking. Only a single test set submission will be allowed to avoid overfitting.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Announcement of challenge's opening: April 1th 2026

- Open for registration: April 1th, 2026
- Training data release: April 1th, 2026
- Validation phase start: May 15th, 2026
- Deadline for test set submission: September 1st, 2026
- Winner and invitation speakers: No later than September 7th, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Radboud University Medical Center approved this challenge protocol on 5/1/2016, with NO. 20162275. Contact person: Geert Litjens, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Science, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands; geert.litjens@radboudumc.nl

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation pipeline will be made public and open source after the launch of the challenge. We will provide a GitHub link for the code of evaluation metrics on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

:The participants are encouraged to upload their code to Github and share the Github link in the PDF submission file.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the prostate cancer prognosis challenge. Only organizing members of the challenge have access to the test case labels during and after the CHIMERA-agentic challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening

- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support, Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of biological males aged 50 years and older who have undergone MRI scanning for prostate cancer.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The target cohort consists of biological males aged 50 years and older who have undergone prostate MRI and biopsy as part of prostate cancer and diagnostic workup.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

multiparametric MRI, H&E; whole slide images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Histopathology whole-slide images are provided in .tif format (.tif, where ***** denotes the subject_id), and prostate MRI scans are provided in .mha format (.mha, where ***** denotes the subject_id). Annotations are provided in a .csv file containing the following columns: pathology_subject_id, MRI_subject_id, and Gleason grading.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

We will provide PSA, age for prostate patients

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

H&E; stained histopathology slide of biopsies from prostate, MRI of a prostate

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm targets eligibility for active surveillance versus definitive local treatment after biopsy. Alongside the binary decision, the algorithm must provide guideline-based reasoning, explicitly identifying dominant evidence (e.g. Gleason Grade Group, biopsy burden, MRI findings) and highlighting factors that contradict active surveillance.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Reliability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Histopathology Imaging: Acquired using the 3D HISTECH PANNORAMIC 1000 histopathology slide scanner at Radboudumc, Nijmegen and CWZ. **mpMRI Imaging:** Acquired using a Siemens 3T scanner at both Radboudumc, Nijmegen, and CWZ, the Netherlands.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The slides were scanned at a resolution of 0.25 micrometers per pixel. The paired mpMRI images were acquired in the axial plane using a Siemens 3T scanner with a standardized imaging protocol that included T1-weighted imaging for anatomical visualization, ADC maps derived from diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) to assess tissue diffusion characteristics, and DWI sequences with multiple b-values for detecting clinically significant prostate cancer.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training set originates from Radboud University Medical Center. The test set was obtained from Radboudumc, CWZ, Karolinska Institute, and several additional contributing institutes. The names of the latter will remain anonymous until final confirmation is obtained.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Prostate biopsy procedures were performed by experienced urologists using standard clinical protocols. Histopathology of biopsy cores was assessed by board-certified pathologists with expertise in genitourinary pathology, following routine diagnostic practice.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a histopathology slide and mpMRI, including T1-weighted imaging, Diffusion-weighted imaging, and ADC map of a prostate. Training and test cases have a weak annotation representing the recurrence event and the time from prostatectomy to the recurrence of the disease in months.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Participants are welcome to use publicly available datasets, including the PANDA benchmark (which provides over 1,000 training cases), to train and test their own models if desired. As the challenge is organized by Radboudumc, access to relevant tools and resources can be facilitated. However, the task does not require training models from

scratch, as pretrained tools are provided. The primary focus of the evaluation is on agent-level reasoning and clinical decision-making rather than representation learning.

For this task, 450 cases with radiologist-annotated reasoning will be provided, comprising 75 training cases, 75 validation cases, and 300 test cases. Of the test cases, 100 constitute an external test set from Karolinska Institute to assess cross-institutional generalizability.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

The pathology reports for all 450 cases are already available, and histopathology-derived ground truth for clinically significant prostate cancer is present. Reasoning annotations will be extracted from the reports and double-checked by radiologists.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The chosen data proportions reflect the agent-centric design of the task. As pretrained foundation models are provided, the training set is intended for calibration and policy design rather than model training from scratch, and therefore requires a limited number of cases. The validation set supports tuning and public feedback, while the majority of cases are reserved for the test set to enable robust and unbiased evaluation of agent-level reasoning and clinical decision-making. This allocation balances expert annotation effort with statistically meaningful assessment of reasoning performance on unseen data.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training data has real-world distribution. Participants should expect data with domain shift/from other institutions in validation and testing. We encourage participants to develop models that generalize well across centers despite domain shifts caused by differences in MRI parameters, staining, and scanners in histopathology. At the same time, we will try to match important characteristics of the development and testing cohorts as much as possible, such as age, Gleason grades, etc.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will publish 75 cases, paired multiparametric MRI and biopsies specifically curated for this challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For all training, validation, and test cases, the reference annotation for eligibility for active surveillance is derived retrospectively from biopsy histopathology and PSA-related clinical variables, in accordance with established clinical guidelines (e.g. EAU/NCCN). Biopsy pathology reports provide the Gleason Grade Group and biopsy burden, which form the primary basis for determining whether criteria for active surveillance are met.

Reasoning annotations describe the clinical decision logic underlying the reference outcome label. These reasoning statements are automatically extracted from structured radiology and pathology reports using large

language models and are subsequently reviewed and validated by expert radiologists based on the available radiology reports and current clinical guidelines. The reasoning explicitly states the key evidence supporting the decision (e.g. MRI findings, lesion characteristics, biopsy grade when available). The same annotation procedure is applied consistently across training, validation, and test cases.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Prior to annotation, annotators were provided with a written annotation protocol describing the clinical objective, the required outputs, and the definition of eligibility for active surveillance according to established guidelines (e.g. EAU/NCCN).

Annotators were instructed to:

- Review the associated radiology and pathology reports for each case.
- Verify extracted structured variables (e.g. PI-RADS score, lesion characteristics, Gleason Grade Group, biopsy burden, PSA-related measures).
- Review and validate reasoning statements automatically extracted using large language models.
- Write or refine one or two concise, clinically grounded reasoning sentences explaining why the patient is eligible or not eligible for active surveillance, explicitly referencing key supporting or excluding factors.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

The ground truth of task 2 is from biopsy WSI and the uncertainty in Gleason Grade Group assignment may arise from sampling limitations in biopsy cores and inter-pathologist variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

NA

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The evaluation metric consists of two folds, reflecting (i) tool selection and outcome prediction)

The first fold evaluates whether the agent selects the appropriate tool and produces accurate predictions. In this task, prostate cancer (PCa) performance is assessed using the standard AUROC metric, which serves as the primary metric for leaderboard ranking.

Fold 2: Reasoning similarity (non-ranking)

To assess similarity between generated reasoning and reference texts, we employ a composite similarity metric that captures semantic, conceptual, and lexical alignment. Semantic similarity is computed using cosine similarity between sentence embeddings extracted with PubMedBERT (NeuML/pubmedbert-base-embeddings). Biomedical concept overlap is quantified using Jaccard similarity over entities extracted with SciSpacy (en_core_sci_lg). Lexical overlap is assessed using simplified BLEU-4 (4-gram precision) and ROUGE-L (longest common subsequence F1).

The final similarity score is defined as:

$$S = w_1 \text{EmbeddingCosine} + w_2 \text{EntityJaccard} + w_3 (\text{BLEU-4} + \text{ROUGE-L}), \sum w_i = 1$$

This metric is used for relative comparison of explanation text and does not measure factual correctness, causal reasoning, or clinical validity.

Expert review of reasoning (top-performing submissions)

For the top five submissions on the leaderboard, domain experts (radiologists) will conduct a qualitative review of the generated explanations. Reasoning will be scored based on predefined criteria, including clinical plausibility, coherence, appropriate use of evidence, and absence of spurious or unsupported claims. Expert scores will be reported separately and will not affect leaderboard ranking.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The evaluation metrics for Task 2 were selected to reflect the dual objectives of accurate treatment decision support and transparent clinical reasoning. Predictive performance is assessed using AUROC, which provides a threshold-independent measure of discrimination and is appropriate for evaluating eligibility for active surveillance versus definitive treatment under potential class imbalance. AUROC aligns with the clinical objective of correctly ranking patients by treatment suitability.

Reasoning quality is evaluated using a composite similarity metric capturing semantic, conceptual, and lexical alignment between model-generated explanations and expert reference reasoning. This reflects the clinical requirement that treatment recommendations be accompanied by guideline-consistent justification. Expert qualitative review of reasoning for top-performing submissions further assesses clinical plausibility and appropriate use of evidence, providing contextual validation without influencing leaderboard ranking.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The final score for each algorithm is computed as a weighted combination of predictive performance and reasoning metrics. For the top five submissions, clinician-evaluated reasoning scores are combined with the two automated reasoning metrics and averaged to obtain the final reasoning score.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The challenge explicitly targets agent-level reasoning and decision transparency, which are essential for clinical trust, interpretability, and safe deployment alongside strong diagnostic performance. Incorporating reasoning quality into the ranking encourages participants to develop agents that not only achieve high predictive accuracy but also generate explanations that are aligned with expert clinical reasoning.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The statistical analysis is designed to provide robust evaluation of patient-level risk prediction, biopsy decision-making, and agent-level reasoning. Performance is assessed on a held-out test set using threshold-independent and clinically meaningful metrics. Uncertainty and variability are quantified using non-parametric, resampling-based methods, which do not rely on distributional assumptions and are appropriate given the moderate sample size and heterogeneous clinical data. Reasoning performance is evaluated on a curated subset with expert annotations.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms is assessed using non-parametric percentile bootstrap resampling on the private test set. For each metric (e.g. ROC-AUC for risk prediction and Clinical Reasoning Agreement Score (CRAS) for reasoning evaluation), bootstrap samples are generated at the case level.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Ranking variability is evaluated using bootstrap-based ranking stability analysis. For each bootstrap resample of the test set, algorithms are re-ranked based on the primary metric

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability is evaluated using bootstrap-based ranking stability analysis. For each bootstrap resample of the test set, algorithms are re-ranked based on the primary metric

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using paired, non-parametric tests on the test set.

Differences in ROC-AUC are evaluated using bootstrap-based paired comparisons.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Cases with missing ground truth labels are excluded from evaluation.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All statistical analyses are performed using Python, primarily leveraging NumPy, SciPy, scikit-learn

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

These further analyses will be discussed in a publication after the challenge.

TASK 3: Prostatectomy Pathology Prediction.

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In a later stage of the prostate cancer care pathway, patients who undergo radical prostatectomy are followed longitudinally using serial prostate-specific antigen (PSA) measurements. Based on postoperative pathology and PSA follow-up, clinicians assess the risk of biochemical recurrence (BCR) to guide subsequent management, including imaging, salvage radiotherapy, and systemic therapy. In this task, participants must develop an AI agent that integrates post-surgical pathology information (including whole-slide images from prostatectomy specimens), biopsy findings, PSA-related clinical variables, and patient characteristics (e.g. age, pre- and post-surgery PSA values), together with preoperative MRI, to estimate time-dependent BCR risk at clinically relevant horizons (e.g. 1, 2, and 5 years).

To lower the entry barrier, the organizers will provide standardized preprocessing and feature extraction tools for prostatectomy whole-slide images, as well as automated Gleason grading tools for both biopsy and prostatectomy specimens, in addition to an MRI-based prostate cancer detection tool. The agent must output quantitative BCR risk estimates accompanied by structured clinical reasoning that identifies the dominant prognostic factors and explains their contribution to recurrence risk, in accordance with established clinical risk stratification frameworks.

Reflecting real-world clinical care, cases may include multiple MRIs and/or biopsies over time, while others may have incomplete or missing modalities. CHIMERA-agent explicitly includes such longitudinal and incomplete cases and requires models to resolve conflicts through transparent reasoning: detecting disagreement across modalities and timepoints, prioritizing evidence given the clinical context, and justifying the final risk estimate. Missingness is intentionally irregular (e.g. absent MRI, incomplete biopsy variables, or missing clinical measures), creating a stress test for robust multimodal reasoning rather than brittle pattern matching.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Prostate cancer, Biochemical recurrence, Prognostic modeling, Longitudinal analysis, Multimodal AI, Explainable AI, Digital pathology, Whole-slide imaging, PSA kinetics, Risk stratification

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Nadieh Khalili – Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

Geert Litjens – Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

Kimmo Kartasalo – Karolinska Institute, Sweden

Martin Eklund – Karolinska Institute, Sweden

Jolique van Ipenburg, , pathologist– Radboud University Medical Center, The Netherlands

Max Ragusi, radiologist – University Medical Center Utrecht, The Netherlands

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Nadieh Khalili, Radboud University Medical Center (Radboudumc), The Netherlands

nadieh.khalili@radboudum.nl

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Clinicians are an integral part of the organizing team. For Task 2, expert radiologists and pathologists are directly involved in defining the task, validating MRI-derived and pathology annotations, and evaluating the reasoning provided by the top five performing teams.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

CHIMERA 2025: <https://chimera.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed during model development and training, including data curation (e.g., excluding training samples), preprocessing, and pre-training or fine-tuning. No user interaction is allowed during inference on the hidden test set.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

External data and pre-trained models are permitted in this competition, provided they are freely and publicly accessible under a permissive open-source license. Examples of such licenses include the Creative Commons license (standard), GNU software or documentation license (standard), BSD license, MIT license, or Open Database license. If participants are uncertain whether a specific dataset's license qualifies as permissive, they should consult the challenge organizers for clarification.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 10 teams will be invited to be part of the challenge manuscript. In addition, we are actively seeking sponsorship for awards. We will provide prize incentives exclusively for open-source submissions. In addition, we will highlight and recognize teams that contribute reusable tools and methodologies to encourage knowledge sharing.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the submission. Only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed up to five co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when citing the overview paper after its publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Interested teams must register for the CHIMERA-agent challenge via chimera-agent.grand-challenge.org. After release of the training dataset, teams may develop their solutions using their own public or private computing resources. Submissions consist of a trained algorithm packaged as a Docker container, which is evaluated on a validation cohort. Teams may participate in one or multiple tasks.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to validate their results multiple times (up to 5) on a validation set before submitting the final results. This can also help participants ensure the submission is in the correct format. Only the best submission will be counted for the official validation ranking. Only a single test set submission will be allowed to avoid overfitting.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Announcement of challenge's opening: April 1th 2026

- Open for registration: April 1th, 2026
- Training data release: April 1th, 2026
- Validation phase start: May 15th, 2026
- Deadline for test set submission: September 1st, 2026
- Winner and invitation speakers: No later than September 7th, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Medical Ethics Committee of Radboud University Medical Center approved this challenge protocol on 5/1/2016, with NO. 20162275. Contact person: Geert Litjens, Department of Pathology, Radboud Institute for Health Science, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands; geert.litjens@radboudumc.nl

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation pipeline will be made public and open source after the launch of the challenge. We will provide a GitHub link for the code of evaluation metrics on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

:The participants are encouraged to upload their code to Github and share the Github link in the PDF submission file.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the prostate cancer prognosis challenge. Only organizing members of the challenge have access to the test case labels during and after the CHIMERA-agent challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Decision support, Prognosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Prediction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final

biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/object(s) from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort consists of biological males aged 50 years and older who have undergone MRI scanning for prostate cancer.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The target cohort consists of biological males aged 50 years and older who have undergone prostate MRI, biopsy, and radical prostatectomy as part of prostate cancer diagnosis and treatment.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

multiparametric MRI, H&E; whole slide images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Histopathology whole-slide images are provided in .tif format (.tif, where *** denotes the subject_id), and prostate MRI scans are provided in .mha format (.mha, where ***** denotes the subject_id). Annotations are provided in a .csv file containing the following columns: pathology_subject_id, MRI_subject_id, recurrence_event, and time_to_recurrence_in_months.**

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

PSA levels over time (pre- and post-prostatectomy), age

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

H&E-stained; histopathology whole-slide images of preoperative prostate biopsy cores and radical prostatectomy specimens, together with multiparametric MRI of the prostate

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm targets time-dependent biochemical recurrence risk following radical prostatectomy. In addition to quantitative risk estimates, the algorithm must produce structured prognostic reasoning that explains how surgical pathology, preoperative imaging, and PSA kinetics contribute to recurrence risk, including handling of incomplete or longitudinal data.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Reliability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Histopathology Imaging: Acquired using the 3D HISTECH PANNORAMIC 1000 histopathology slide scanner at Radboudumc, Nijmegen and CWZ. **mpMRI Imaging:** Acquired using a Siemens 3T scanner at both Radboudumc, Nijmegen, and CWZ, the Netherlands.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The slides were scanned at a resolution of 0.25 micrometers per pixel. The paired mpMRI images were acquired in the axial plane using a Siemens 3T scanner with a standardized imaging protocol that included T1-weighted imaging for anatomical visualization, ADC maps derived from diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) to assess tissue diffusion characteristics, and DWI sequences with multiple b-values for detecting clinically significant prostate cancer.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The training set originates from Radboud University Medical Center. The test set was obtained from Radboudumc, CWZ, Karolinska Institute, and several additional contributing institutes. The names of the latter will remain anonymous until final confirmation is obtained.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Radical prostatectomy procedures were performed by experienced urologic surgeons in routine clinical care. Prostatectomy specimens were processed and reviewed by board-certified pathologists specializing in prostate cancer, and postoperative PSA follow-up was conducted as part of standard oncologic surveillance.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training and test cases both represent a histopathology slide from biopsies and prostatectomy and mpMRI, including T1-weighted imaging, Diffusion-weighted imaging, and ADC map of a prostate. Training and test cases have a weak annotation representing the recurrence event and the time from prostatectomy to the recurrence of the disease in months.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Participants are welcome to use publicly available datasets, including the Leopard benchmark (which provides over 1,000 training cases), to train and test their own models if desired. As the challenge is organized by Radboudumc, access to relevant tools and resources can be facilitated. However, the task does not require training models from scratch, as pretrained tools are provided. The primary focus of the evaluation is on agent-level reasoning and clinical decision-making rather than representation learning.

For this task, 400 cases with radiologist-annotated reasoning will be provided, comprising 75 training cases, 75 validation cases, and 250 test cases. Of the test cases, 100 originate from Karolinska Institute and serve as an external test set to assess cross-institutional generalizability.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

The pathology reports for all 400 cases are already available, and histopathology-derived ground truth for clinically significant prostate cancer is present. Reasoning annotations will be extracted from the reports and double-checked by radiologists.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The chosen data proportions reflect the agent-centric design of the task. As pretrained foundation models are provided, the training set is intended for calibration and policy design rather than model training from scratch, and therefore requires a limited number of cases. The validation set supports tuning and public feedback, while the majority of cases are reserved for the test set to enable robust and unbiased evaluation of agent-level reasoning and clinical decision-making. This allocation balances expert annotation effort with statistically meaningful assessment of reasoning performance on unseen data.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training data has real-world distribution. Participants should expect data with domain shift/from other institutions in validation and testing. We encourage participants to develop models that generalize well across centers despite domain shifts caused by differences in MRI parameters, staining, and scanners in histopathology. At the same time, we will try to match important characteristics of the development and testing cohorts as much

as possible, such as age, Gleason grades, etc.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will publish 75 cases, paired multiparametric MRI and biopsies and prostatectomy specifically curated for this challenge.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For all training, validation, and test cases, the reference annotation for biochemical recurrence (BCR) is derived from longitudinal postoperative PSA follow-up after radical prostatectomy. BCR is defined according to standard clinical criteria (e.g. confirmed PSA rise ≥ 0.2 ng/mL), and time-to-recurrence is recorded in months. Patients without recurrence during follow-up are treated as censored observations. Reasoning annotations describe the clinical decision logic underlying the reference outcome label. These reasoning statements are automatically extracted from structured clinical and pathology reports using large language models and are subsequently reviewed and validated by expert clinicians (pathologists and oncologists) based on the available reports and current clinical guidelines. The reasoning explicitly highlights the dominant prognostic factors contributing to recurrence risk (e.g. Gleason Grade Group, surgical margins, extracapsular extension, PSA kinetics).

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For Task 3, annotators were provided with a dedicated annotation protocol describing the definition of biochemical recurrence (BCR) and the relevant prognostic factors used in postoperative risk assessment.

Annotators were instructed to:

- Review postoperative pathology reports, prostatectomy whole-slide images (at the report level), and longitudinal PSA follow-up data.
- Confirm recurrence status and time-to-recurrence based on standard clinical definitions.
- Review and validate reasoning statements automatically extracted using large language models.
- Write or refine one or two concise, clinically grounded reasoning sentences identifying the dominant prognostic factors contributing to recurrence risk (e.g. Gleason Grade Group, surgical margins, extracapsular extension, PSA kinetics).
- Explicitly note uncertainty or missing information where relevant and reflect this in the reasoning.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

NA

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Biochemical recurrence status is derived from longitudinal PSA measurements using standardized clinical definitions. Potential sources of error include variability in PSA assay timing and missing follow-up measurements. These are addressed by treating non-recurrent cases as censored observations and explicitly modeling follow-up time.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

NA

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The evaluation metric consists of two folds, reflecting (i) tool selection and prediction performance and (ii) quality of generated reasoning.

Fold 1: Predictive performance (tool selection and outcome prediction)

The first fold evaluates whether the agent selects the appropriate tool and produces accurate predictions. In this task, BCR time to recurrent index, which serves as the primary metric for leaderboard ranking.

Fold 2: Reasoning similarity (non-ranking)

To assess similarity between generated reasoning and reference texts, we employ a composite similarity metric that captures semantic, conceptual, and lexical alignment. Semantic similarity is computed using cosine similarity between sentence embeddings extracted with PubMedBERT (NeuML/pubmedbert-base-embeddings). Biomedical concept overlap is quantified using Jaccard similarity over entities extracted with SciSpacy (en_core_sci_lg). Lexical overlap is assessed using simplified BLEU-4 (4-gram precision) and ROUGE-L (longest common subsequence F1).

The final similarity score is defined as: $\text{Score} = \frac{1}{\sum} (\text{EmbeddingCosine} + 2 \text{EntityJaccard} + 3(\text{BLEU-4} + \text{ROUGE-L}))$

This metric is used for relative comparison of explanation text and does not measure factual correctness, causal reasoning, or clinical validity.

Expert review of reasoning (top-performing submissions)

For the top five submissions on the leaderboard, domain experts (radiologists) will conduct a qualitative review of the generated explanations. Reasoning will be scored based on predefined criteria, including clinical plausibility, coherence, appropriate use of evidence, and absence of spurious or unsupported claims. Expert scores will be reported separately and will not affect leaderboard ranking.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The evaluation metrics for Task 3 were chosen to reflect the objectives of accurate prognostic modeling and interpretable risk assessment. Prognostic performance is assessed using the concordance index (C-index), which is well suited for time-to-event outcomes with censored data and aligns with the clinical goal of correctly ranking patients by biochemical recurrence risk following radical prostatectomy.

Reasoning quality is evaluated using the same composite similarity metric as in Tasks 1 and 2, ensuring consistency across tasks while capturing alignment between model-generated explanations and expert prognostic reasoning. Expert qualitative review of reasoning for top-performing submissions complements the automated metrics by assessing clinical plausibility, coherence, and appropriate integration of longitudinal and pathological evidence, without affecting leaderboard ranking.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The final score for each algorithm is computed as a weighted combination of predictive performance and reasoning metrics. For the top five submissions, clinician-evaluated reasoning scores are combined with the two automated reasoning metrics and averaged to obtain the final reasoning score.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The challenge explicitly targets agent-level reasoning and decision transparency, which are essential for clinical trust, interpretability, and safe deployment alongside strong diagnostic performance. Incorporating reasoning quality into the ranking encourages participants to develop agents that not only achieve high predictive accuracy but also generate explanations that are aligned with expert clinical reasoning.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The statistical analysis is designed to provide robust evaluation of patient-level risk prediction, biopsy decision-making, and agent-level reasoning. Performance is assessed on a held-out test set using threshold-independent and clinically meaningful metrics. Uncertainty and variability are quantified using non-parametric, resampling-based methods, which do not rely on distributional assumptions and are appropriate given the moderate sample size and heterogeneous clinical data. Reasoning performance is evaluated on a curated subset with expert annotations.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms is assessed using non-parametric percentile bootstrap resampling on the private test set. For each metric (e.g. ROC-AUC for risk prediction and Clinical Reasoning Agreement Score (CRAS) for reasoning evaluation), bootstrap samples are generated at the case level.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Ranking variability is evaluated using bootstrap-based ranking stability analysis. For each bootstrap resample of the test set, algorithms are re-ranked based on the primary metric

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Ranking variability is evaluated using bootstrap-based ranking stability analysis. For each bootstrap resample of the test set, algorithms are re-ranked based on the primary metric

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical significance of performance differences between algorithms is assessed using paired, non-parametric tests on the test set.

Differences in ROC-AUC are evaluated using bootstrap-based paired comparisons.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Cases with missing ground truth labels are excluded from evaluation.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

All statistical analyses are performed using Python, primarily leveraging NumPy, SciPy, scikit-learn

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

These further analyses will be discussed in a publication after the challenge.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

1. Sung, Hyuna, Jacques Ferlay, Rebecca L. Siegel, Mathieu Laversanne, Isabelle Soerjomataram, Ahmedin Jemal, and Freddie Bray. "Global cancer statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries." *CA: a cancer journal for clinicians* 71, no. 3 (2021): 209-249.
2. <https://chimera.grand-challenge.org/>

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A